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**NATIONWIDE VALUES AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT
IN MODERN CONDITIONS**

**ОБЩЕНАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ЦЕННОСТИ И ИХ РАЗВИТИЕ
В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ**

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Abstract. The article deals with the formation of national values in the context of globalization and in these circumstances, human values remain the major connecting element between people and States. It is the system of values is becoming a relevant today, since they define the behavior of human activities and are a source of activity of the subject of social development. The solution to the problem of national values is associated with a number of fundamental issues. In modern society, the upbringing of young people requires personal characteristics drill through forming, ensure the development of value orientations. The value is interpreted as the significance of objects and phenomena, satisfying the need of vital activity of the subjects. The main problem of the choice of values is to find nearly evaporated; and an acceptable combination values of all, not the deification of one of them. The main value of modern youth lifestyle characteristics that are considered when generating the value orientations, fixed: failure or lack of sustainable values; openness to experimentation, innovation and change; the adoption of a diversity of positions and its approval; separation as away of getting used to changing social situations; focus on the present rather than the future and the past; the transformation from an external to an internal verification of its existence, which is reflected in the first of all on oneself and the smallest on the support of the State; the propensity to enter into informal associations and societies with a multi-polar orientation; determination to mobility geographical, social and cultural. This, in modern conditions of diversity of values, development of national values issue requires a more complete study, both theoretical and practical levels.

Аннотация. В статье речь идет о формировании общенациональных ценностей в условиях глобализации и в этих условиях общечеловеческие ценности остаются важнейшим связующим элементом между народами и государствами. Именно система ценностей приобретает сегодня актуальный характер, так как она определяют цель деятельности человека и является источником активности субъекта общественного развития. Решение проблемы общенациональных ценностей связана с решением ряда принципиальных вопросов. В современном обществе процесс воспитания молодежи требует детализирования

характеристики личностных форм образования, обеспечивающих развитие ценностных ориентаций. Ценность воспринимается как значимость объектов и явлений, удовлетворяющих необходимость жизнедеятельности субъектов. Основная проблема выбора ценностей заключается в нахождении гармонии и приемлемом сочетании всех ценностей, а не в обожествлении одной из них. Протекание эволюции общенациональных ценностей у современной молодежи продиктовано сложностями преобразования экономических, политических и социальных условий, но от того, какие ценности будут преобладать, зависит ее будущее. Главные ценностные характеристики образа жизни современной молодежи, которые рассматриваются при формировании ценностных ориентаций, фиксированы: непризнание или неимение устойчивых ценностей; открытость опыту, инновациям и переменам; принятие многообразия позиций и его утверждение; обособление, как способ привыкания к изменяющимся социальным ситуациям; направленность на настоящее, а не на будущее или прошлое; трансформация от внешней к внутренней проверке своего существования, что отражается в прежде всего на собственных силах и самое малое на поддержке государства; склонность к вступлению в неформальные объединения и общества с многополюсной ориентацией; решимость к подвижности географической, социальной и культурной. Таким образом, в современных условиях разнообразие ценностей, вопрос развития общенациональных ценностей требует более полного исследования, как на теоретическом, так и на практическом уровне.

Ключевые слова: общенациональные, социальные, нравственные, ценности, общества, деятельность, потребность.

Keywords: national, social, moral, values, society, need.

Mankind is losing its values, that for centuries provided mutual confidence among peoples and respect between people, falls the authority of parents, teachers, forgotten traditions and lost interest in social and spiritual values of life.

In our opinion, the main reason is the destruction of traditional values and the lack of formation of a new system of values, appropriate to modern conditions. Now, for most people lost value and traditional view of truth, goodness and beauty, relaxed moral–ethical norms.

Social and moral values and their system does not find justification and reinforcement in public life, becoming unacceptable for a modern person, as he sees them not as base of well–being and survival.

Today's transformation of traditional values makes it necessary to develop a new understanding of their structure and content system. Here it is necessary to take into account the main views on perceptions of culture, traditions and values should be able to synthesize the main philosophical theories and doctrines of religions.

The focus on values should be geared to prospective trends of development of society, in which annex intellectual and emotional capacity is carried out harmoniously and includes a moral view of truth, kindness, justice, beauty, and love.

In modern conditions for identifying values, consider the main existing theoretical provisions of their essence and types, and then pay attention to the problems of choice of value systems.

Value as a phenomenon apparent in value orientations of the individual are psychopedagogical education, in which compressed there is direct and indirect relevance to human environment and to himself. On this basis the totality of a variety of human relationships to the world and to itself, caused the entire system needs and system of symbols and cultural tools, forms a system–hierarchical–world values.

As one of the most important elements of human spiritual culture values allow the individual and society to reproduce social relations, public relations and ensure their development.

It should be noted that in most Western views there is no systematic approach to the study of values, there is no clear definition of entity concepts of values, the same values are interpreted largely subjective–psychological, as the intent, purpose, installation, etc., an individual or a narrow, isolated group of individuals. But it is the individual, private values those are the least interesting and important, even if you keep in mind the individual. In scientific cognition values tend to be of a collective nature, starting with the values of a particular scientific community and ending values culture as a whole.

Values to specific theories can be divided into two types: internal and external. The internal structure of the theory itself, come in as integral components, external relate to which exists and develops theory. Between internal and external values of relative border. The value of the second kind are extremely varied. Then there are external values cover a wide range of designs, rules, regulations, assessments, principles, etc., they impact on forming theory and its subsequent evolution.

In mastering the role values values. The traditional essence of human values remains the most important binding element between peoples and States. These values are relevant for all people regardless of their social class, national, professional affiliation. According to many scientists, based on universal values, perhaps, develop cooperation between peoples [1, p.12].

To reveal the essence of the values, you must provide an analysis of all possible system needs through relevance, unity of subject and object.

Human values, by analogy with the requirements are divided into three types — biological; social; ideal.

The goal of each individual is serving his family, nationality, society, State, world, meaning it is designed to serve others and to meet their ideal requirements.

Biological and social values implement the day-to-day needs for food, clothing, as well as communication, group membership, self–actualization, they are a necessary but not sufficient condition for the realization of the exact ideal values that human development, nation and society. And ideal values and their particular role is manifested in socio–cultural activities.

However, the formation of national values in the context of globalization to address a number of problems associated with the contradiction in globalization process itself; change in socio–cultural environment, in which people and nations are immersed in everyday social practices; influence on the formation of individual and public consciousness, attitudes to social processes and value settings that they pursue.

The above circumstances are complicating the dialogue of cultures, the process of formation of the humanitarian national values among young people. The process of transforming the public consciousness under the modern global system with different approaches to the modernization of society cannot occur spontaneously and requires objective axiological theory basis.

In socio–cultural activities the applied scientific method is a system of categories of values, principles, methods, designs and so on, which guide the scientific world in its activities.

It is precise that the values allow people to meet their spiritual needs. The whole set of values for the person represented in a hierarchical manner, which are: biological, social and ideal values.

Given the system of socio–cultural values are separated on different grounds: on the origin of values; in their essential characteristic; by their creators and users; on the kinds of needs.

Hence it can be concluded that the choice of values is to find harmony and optimal combination of values that implement the whole system of human needs [2, p. 138]. Study on the system of values is becoming today a strategic character, as they define the behavior of human activities and are a source of activity of the subject of social development.

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